

Milton in an Age of Stupidity

BLAINE GRETEMAN

University of Iowa

ABSTRACT John Milton had little patience with those whom he considered “stupid.” This article examines the various contexts in which Milton expressed contempt for political opponents or those he deemed as lacking common sense, good judgment, or intelligence. It suggests that we can learn as much from Milton’s intolerance for uninformed opinions as we can from his much-discussed tolerance for dissent.

KEYWORDS stupidity, Milton, race, religion, education

We live in stupid times. Although the fires scorching “this pendant globe” can be seen from space, the current president of the United States, formerly a reality television star, declares that “global warming is a total, and very expensive, hoax!”¹ During the coronavirus pandemic, residents of Flint Michigan begged for water clean enough to wash their hands, doctors and nurses begged for simple protective masks, and billionaires like David Geffen posted selfies of themselves in “self seclusion” in their yachts and summer homes. “It totally makes sense,” the president of a yachting company told the *New York Times*, “you’re keeping your family contained in a very small, should-be-clean environment. And going from your car . . . to your private jet right onto the tarmac. And from there, right onto your yacht, and not having to deal with the public.”² Milton has much to say about such failures of ecological stewardship and moral governance. But what he most often says is that they are “stupid.” In this way, he may be the ultimate poet for our moment.

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Milton possessed a promethean vocabulary. He could quote the canon of biblical and classical literature from memory, in English or in the originals. He uses sesquipedalian titles like *Tetrachordon*, *Colasterion*, and *Areopagitica*. And in moments of despair his characters shout six-penny phrases like “Shameful garrulity.”³ So it may be surprising to consider that Milton’s favorite epithet is also the choice insult of kindergartners and surly teens: stupid. He calls people and things “stupid” repeatedly, both in English and in his otherwise elegant Latin, where he never hesitates to label his targets not just “stupidus” and “stolidus” but profoundly, superlatively, “stupidissimus” and “stolidissimus.”⁴

As my students would say, this is “relatable.” Consider how much more fitting the Declaration of Independence would be to contemporary America if Thomas Jefferson had replaced his mealy-mouthed “we hold these truths to be self evident, that all men are created equal,” with Milton’s pissy introduction to *The Tenure of Kings and Magistrates*: “No man who knows ought, can be so stupid to deny that all men naturally were borne free” (CM 5:8). Like Benjamin Franklin’s suggestion that our national bird should be the turkey—because, although it was “vain and silly,” it was also suicidally aggressive—this was undeniably a missed opportunity to express the nation’s ethos.⁵

But of course many people are exactly stupid enough to deny equality and other truths, as Milton never tires of reminding us. Indeed, just as unfit readers in Milton’s world outnumber the fit few, the stupid overwhelmingly outnumber the reasonable. After an anonymous author attacked Milton’s *The Doctrine and Discipline of Divorce*, for example, Milton responded that the author’s failure to cite the most recent, second edition of the tract was “a singular note of his stupidity” and evidence “that his Trade is not to meddle with Books” (CM 4:237). The gibe about his “trade” is just one of Milton’s many allusions to his suspicion that his opponent is a laborer, not a scholar. But he also thought many scholars were stupid. In *An Apology for Smectymnuus* he attacks Bishop John Hall, who held a doctorate from Cambridge University and who was known for his learned poetry, his devotional literature, and, according to Milton, for his “itching pedantry” (3:312). “Note how stupid he is,” Milton sneers, “to expose himself” as a fool in print (3:293). Hall does this by “sycophanting and misnaming the worke of his adversary,” which, admittedly, is pretty dumb (3:292–93). Even Hall’s use of extensive textual notes—long the badge of scholarly, if dry, writing—is a sign for Milton of “his barren stupidity,” as Hall unloads “the foolish frigate of his unseasonable authorities” into the margins (3:334). By this standard,

almost everyone I know and work with is incredibly stupid, and my writing is a monument to my own stupidity (something the anonymous “Reviewer 2” helpfully pointed out about the manuscript of my first book). In this article I’ve been reduced to footnoting tweets, which surely proves our world is a nightmare version of Milton’s *Paradise of Fools*, populated by “embryos and idiots, eremites and friars, / White, black, and gray, with all their trumpery” (*PL* 3.474–75).

Milton sees this kind of stupidity everywhere he looks. He accuses Catholics of “willful stupidity” (*CM* 3:253). He says it is “a stupidnes” to refuse divorce when a marriage has been “brokn and disjoynted from love and peace” (4:98–99). He attacks “stupid and malicious monks” (3:9). And he saves his harshest words for some of his own former allies who seized power in the Parliament and English church only to betray the cause, “executing thir places like children of the devil, unfaithfully, unjustly, unmercifully, and where not corruptly, stupidly” (10:323). This, by the way, is a near-perfect distillation of the Trump administration’s governing style, which has been defended by one of its chief loyalists as being so “incoherent” that it was “incapable of forming a quid pro quo.”⁶ Attempted corruption, bargained down to an admission of stupidity. Milton, however, would probably not be persuaded to consider stupidity a mitigating factor, since injustice and faithlessness appear to have stupidity as both their cause and effect. Shakespeare wrote that “nothing will come of nothing,” but Milton intuited the “meaning, not the name” of “stupid is as stupid does.”⁷

By now, most Miltonists will probably suspect (or object) that Milton means something more nuanced when he calls someone “stupid” than when my stropky teen daughter tells me I’m stupid for asking her to clean her room.⁸ He doesn’t. The *Oxford English Dictionary* (*OED*) cites Milton himself, in *The Tenure of Kings and Magistrates*, to illustrate the use of “stupid” to refer to a person who is “slow to learn or understand; lacking intelligence or perceptiveness; acting without common sense or good judgement. In later use also as a more general term of abuse.”⁹ This puts Milton in the company of writers like Joseph Addison (“A Man, who cannot write with Wit on a proper Subject, is dull and stupid”), Percy Bysshe Shelley (“his lordship stands and wracks his stupid brains”), and Twitter user @dave17759518, who warned in a tweet of November 27, 2018, that “the human race better get a grip and stop acting stupid or there won’t be anything left of the earth.”¹⁰

The quotation of tweets in the *OED* was not something I had encountered before I began investigating Milton's use of "stupid," but I think it speaks to the timeliness of his predilection for the term. Most words in the *OED* that get the Twitter treatment are neologisms, like "mansplain," "selfie," and "alt-right." The majority of them, such as "awesomesauce," would leave Milton bewildered.¹¹ But even if the seventeenth-century poet would have disagreed with the sentiment of @denisedagee, who is immortalized in the *OED* for tweeting "I wanna get drunk. Like stupid drunk," Milton would have understood her completely.¹²

Indeed we find this adverbial use of "stupid," meaning "to a degree that causes a person to lose the ability to think clearly or control his or her actions," in book 8 of *Paradise Lost*.¹³ There Satan becomes "stupidly good" from staring at the intoxicatingly "heavenly form" of Eve. The poem also seems to imply that Raphael and Adam get a little stupid when their eyes are "shot" with the "darts of desire" that seem to be part of her inebriating effect (8.62–63). Usually, according to Milton, becoming stupid is bad, although these cases complicate the picture, since one is described as "good" and the other describes an experience visited upon a supposedly perfect human and an unfallen angel. But it is a mark of just how bad Satan is that he's better off stupid. "This isn't a teaching moment in the poem," as Christine Hoffman notes, "it is *only* a stupid one, for Satan exists still hell bent on destruction."¹⁴ And Eve's darts of desire are connected to Adam's troubling assertion that all "higher knowledge in her presence falls / Degraded," which is a fancy way of complaining that she makes him stupider than he would normally be (8.551–52).¹⁵ As John Reichert writes, "to say that Adam's higher knowledge has fallen, and does fall, degraded in Eve's presence is not to say that Adam has fallen or is likely to," but that he's capable of falling, "and he knows it."¹⁶ For Adam to demonstrate a capacity for stupidity is not to say that he is stupid. Most of the time he's a genius, engaging in spontaneous taxonomy, theology, and cosmology.¹⁷ But freedom to fall also means the freedom to do incredibly dumb things. In short, even in Paradise, Milton can't seem to imagine a world without stupidity.

Maybe this is partly Milton's method of accommodating divine truths to what he sees as the limited understanding of us doltish humans. Or maybe when the muse visited Milton nightly to "plant eyes" in his mind and "Purge and disperse" all mists, he was able to see that Satan's ogling Eve introduced a very familiar form of stupidity to our planet (*PL* 3.53–54). In any event, a capacity for profound stupidity was for Milton a defining

human trait, and human history after the Fall is largely a story of idiotic behavior. This at least is how the archangel Michael sees it:

O that men
 (Canst thou believe?) should be so stupid grown,
 While yet the patriarch lived, who scaped the Flood,
 As to forsake the living God, and fall
 To worship their own work in wood and stone
 For gods! (12.115–20)

The “doom of Nonsense” that C. S. Lewis describes as Satan’s plight is, in other words, a doom shared by all of us.¹⁸ Whether it is a punishment or a flaw, to be human, as to be Satan, is to experience “the horrible co-existence of a subtle and incessant intellectual activity with an incapacity to understand anything.”¹⁹

Although this kind of degenerative stupidity is still novel enough to shock the angel, Milton finds it a depressingly familiar pattern. And if individuals and nations are not already stupid, he worries that they are always at risk of lapsing into stupor or being deluded into making stupid decisions by frauds and hucksters. We should therefore “amend our lives with all speed,” warns Milton in *Of True Religion*, lest “we run into that stupidly, which we now seek all means so warily to avoid” (CM 6:179–80). This is also Milton’s fear in *Areopagitica*, where he cautions that in the quest to prevent schism and dissension “we may as soon fall again into a gross conforming stupidity” (4:349). Milton is a humanist, but for him that does not mean celebrating the human so much as combatting this wayward human tendency. It requires constant vigilance and struggle, because it is easy and natural—even pleasurable—to lapse into a state of numb, uncritical, unintelligent, bare existence. Sometimes, we all want to get stupid drunk.

And of course someone is always happy to take the money and pour the drink. Such is the case with Comus, the tempter in Milton’s *Maske* who tries to persuade the Lady that his magic elixir “will cure all straight, one sip of this / Will bathe the drooping spirits in delight / Beyond the bliss of dreams.”²⁰ To have an active and engaged conscience is to subject oneself to “trouble and melancholy,” and Milton suggests in *Of True Religion* that organized religion is essentially a cartel designed to profit from that pain by serving up easy answers (CM 6:178). Catholicism in particular is a “more pleasing Doctrine” that offers “easy Confession, easy Absolution, Pardons, Indulgences, Masses . . . both quick and dead, *Agnus Dei*’s, relics, and the

like” (6:179). All of which is permission to be a “fool” and behave “stupidly” (6:179). Surveying the history of the church in Britain, Milton finds a parade of Catholic clergy dedicated to keeping “in awe the superstitious multitude” with the effect of leaving them “gross and stupid as themselves” (10:135). The supposedly “reformed” English church has fared little better, according to Milton, containing many within its ranks who are happy to “bring a num and chil stupidity of soul, an unactive blindnesse of minde, upon the people by their leaden doctrine” (3:214).

No cartel would be complete without lawyers and politicians who cater to and profit from such stupidity. The law calls for “prudent circumspection,” and Milton notes that this is not the same as being “stupidly and tamely patient” when we can see that we’re being cheated or lied to (CM 3.2:487). But tyrants and their defenders demand stupid and tame patience, employing dogmatic, literalistic arguments that require us to ignore the evidence of our own eyes. We would call such arguments “gaslighting,” a practice that succeeds by making its subjects stupid and tame. For Milton, King Charles’s *Eikon Basilike* is the *magnum opus* of gaslighting, from its arguments to its engravings, which depict the vanquished king as an innocent saint and martyr whose conduct was not only legal, but “perfect.”²¹

Although he was tried and convicted for pursuing his personal interest rather than the good of the country, Charles and his defenders maintained that the trial had actually “found not matter for any Impeachment, nor ground for the least Reproach.”²² Milton sets out both to destroy this defense in *Eikonoklastes* and to make clear that anything short of killing the king would have been “stupid,” leaving the people of England “not worth the name of a Nation, but a race of Idiots” (CM 5:254). To borrow a formula from Jan Kott, this is Milton our contemporary.²³

Or at least this is the Milton I agree with and can relate to—the one who was too angry to be civil and too irritated to be nice. His stupid and corrupt targets are essentially the same ones we find all around us today, only heightened by the stupefying power of the Internet. Milton’s stupid and corrupt monks look like rank amateurs when stacked against the likes of Donald Trump, who used an impeachment case against him as an opportunity to raise tens of millions of dollars, or the televangelist Jim Bakker, a felon convicted for swindling his flock and using their tax-exempt donations to buy Rolls Royces and mansions, but who emerged from prison and convinced his followers to build him an even more lavish compound and television studio. He now broadcasts prophecies about the coming end times and sells books and survival supplies to his followers (for \$1,000,

you can ride out the apocalypse eating tacos, hamburgers, and pancakes from emergency food buckets that are guaranteed to last for twenty-five years).²⁴ These are the self-proclaimed moral and political guardians of our nation, where a recent confirmation hearing for appointment to the highest court in the land turned on whether and how often the candidate had become “blackout drunk” and included him shouting, “I like beer!”²⁵ Other countries have their own stupidities--wherever they fell on the question of Brexit, Britons seem to agree that their politicians and those on the opposing side are “stupid, useless, idiots.”²⁶ But as an American in the age of Trump, I truly feel seen by Milton.²⁷

Perhaps Milton would characterize his attacks on stupidity as “zeal,” which he says can take the form either of “ardor” for the good or of intense “indignation” at evil.²⁸ Statements of a “ventrous edge, utter’d in the height of zeal,” may be offensive, or mean, or hurtful, but that’s the whole point, because they are part of a righteous battle for the truth (CM 4:326). I think, however, that it would be a mistake to say that Milton matters now because he offers an example of righteous zeal that should be emulated. In reckoning with my own teaching of Milton—and the way Milton was taught to me—I’ve needed to come to terms with the way that teaching is implicated in and by Milton’s elitism, misogyny, and white supremacy. As Stephen Jablonski insists, in Milton’s “ideal world individuals and whole nations would rise or fall to whatever level their abilities merited in a hierarchy of rational excellence. Those at the very bottom would be slaves in some sort to the rest since they would deserve nothing more.”²⁹ And as Jablonski reminds us, Milton did not hesitate to racialize this theory of “rational excellence.”³⁰ It undergirds Milton’s acceptance of natural slavery and the curse on Ham’s “vicious race” that Michael pronounces in *Paradise Lost* and that Milton’s original readers would have understood as a clear etiology of the nascent African slave trade (12.104). Indeed, Milton’s ideas about stupidity, like his ideas of “rational excellence,” are sometimes racialized. “The lower orders,” he writes in the *Second Defense*, “stupefied by the wicked arts of priests, had not yet degenerated into a barbarism viler than what disgraces the Indians, stupidest of mortals” (CM 8:6). The lower orders of Europeans are the stupidest people in existence. But only because they have sunk, through repeated degradation, to an even more abject state of stupidity than to the one Milton believes is natural to other races.

This does not mean that Milton is not a great poet and thinker, but it does mean he’s an imperfect human, just as his readers and critics have been, and that some of his ideas are harmful or dangerous if left unchallenged. To his

lasting credit, this is something he would not dispute. Thanks to critics such as Jablonski, and elsewhere in this issue of *Milton Studies*, Daniel Shore and Reginald Wilburn, we have begun to grapple with the racial legacies of Milton's works. To understand why Milton matters now, we need to understand both that his works endorse the natural freedom of white Europeans and that they validate the natural slavery of nearly everyone else.

We also need to interrogate Milton's ubiquitous charges of stupidity, which he sees in moral terms—just as he does slavery and nonwhite ethnicity. His rage at the stupid is ultimately driven by a sense that he's entitled to a better, more understanding world, run by people who see things his way, and almost certainly by people who resemble him. For me at least, this is uncomfortably familiar. At the root of my anger at my stupid high school classmates, my stupid family members who've ruined the holidays, the stupid administrators who are ruining my job, and the stupid politicians who are ruining our country, there is an obvious feeling of moral as well as intellectual superiority. It is akin to that "sense of injured merit" in *Paradise Lost* that prompts Satan's contempt and that ultimately recoils upon him (1.98).

While we often see the stupid as victimizers and invest them with malicious agency, stupidity can be systemic or even chemical (as in the case of being stupid drunk), and it can complicate agency in ways that are easier to ignore. To be stupid as an effect of gaslighting is to be a victim of a process, but it is difficult to see the angry mob that way when it is rallying to deny your right to exist. We rightly draw a hard line on sexual assault, drunken or not, and are outraged when institutions ignore, dismiss, or diminish the voices of victims with the idea of a "stupid mistake." But most of us have been, or have been around someone, who was so chemically impaired that they were not in control of their own actions. In such cases, withering Miltonic contempt will not go far toward restoring true accountability, which must be grounded in some sense of shared humanity. This is what we ultimately lose when we encounter an other and see or hear only stupidity. Milton demonstrates this with painful clarity in Prologue 7, when he quips that creeping legalese and ignorant use of academic jargon in the universities threatens to make his peers at Cambridge University sound like they are speaking the gibberish of the "Indians I think, or not even human" (*Americanus credo, aut ne humanus quidem*; CM 12:276–77). Milton is such a gifted student of languages and human psychology, yet here he's content with the schoolboy's lazy habit of calling anything he doesn't understand "stupid" and wrapping it up with a racist joke. I think

it is pretty safe to say that if he had never transcended that habit, few of his contemporaries, and even fewer of his posterity, would have found his work, “in English, or other tongue, prosing or versing . . . likely to live” (3.1:235)

The key to that transcendence, as Milton indicated in the personal motto he took late in life, is that “My strength is made perfect in weakness.”³¹ The Milton who condemns nearly everything and everyone around him as “stupid” is often compelling, and it is undeniably exciting to follow his muscular thought. But this is a pleasure akin to following the pyrotechnics of Satan, who also believes that “to be weak is miserable” (*PL* 1.157). Compare that vaunting voice to this one, recognizing and revealing its own limitations in book 3 of *Paradise Lost*:

Seasons return, but not to me returns
Day, or the sweet approach of ev’n or morn,
Or sight of vernal bloom, or summer’s rose,
Or flocks, or herds, or human face divine. (3.41–44)

This is the Milton who cultivates the capacity to appreciate beauty, even divinity, in what he cannot see or fully understand. And after we’ve exposed, reveled in, and destroyed our stupid society, this Milton may still be of use when we begin the harder work of rebuilding it.

NOTES

1. John Milton, *Paradise Lost*, in *The Complete Poetry and Essential Prose*, ed. William Kerrigan, John Rumrich, and Stephen M. Fallon (New York, 2007), 2.1052 (subsequent quotations from Milton’s verse are cited parenthetically from this edition); Twitter.com, 9:13 AM, December 6, 2013.

2. Alex Williams and Jonah Engel Bromwich, “The Rich Are Preparing for Coronavirus Differently,” *New York Times*, March 5, 2020.

3. So laments Samson in *Samson Agonistes*, line 491.

4. *Pro Populo Anglicano Defensio*, in vol. 7 of *The Works of John Milton*, 18 vols., ed. Frank Allen Patterson et al. (New York, 1931–42), 206; and *Pro Populo Anglicano Defensio Secunda*, in vol. 8 of *The Works of John Milton*, ed. Patterson et al., 6. All subsequent quotations from Milton’s prose, unless otherwise indicated, are taken from this edition and cited parenthetically as CM.

5. Benjamin Franklin, letter to Sarah Bache, January 26, 1784, National Archives, <https://founders.archives.gov/documents/Franklin/01-41-02-0327>.

6. Lindsey Graham, quoted in Matt Stieb, “Lindsey Graham: Trump Administration Is Too ‘Incoherent’ to Pull Off a Quid Pro Quo,” *New York Magazine*, November 6, 2019.

7. William Shakespeare, *King Lear*, ed. Kenneth Muir (New York, 1991), 1.1.89; and *Paradise Lost* 7.5.
8. See, for example R. Musgrave, who argues that one of Milton's key uses of stupid "is no stumbling block, if 'stupid' is taken in its seventeenth-century sense of 'destitute of sensation, consciousness, thought, or feeling,'" in "Is the Devil an Ass," *The Review of English Studies* 21, no. 84 (1945): 313.
9. *OED*, "stupid," def. A1.
10. Joseph Addison, *Spectator* 291, February 2, 1711, in *The Spectator With Notes and a General Index* (Philadelphia, 1822), 346; Percy Bysshe Shelley, "Peter Bell the Third," in *The Poetical Works*, ed. Mary Wollstonecraft Shelley (London, 1889), 7.10-11; @dave17759518; all qtd. in *OED*, "stupid."
11. The *Oxford English Dictionary* defines the term as "extremely good; excellent," and cites the exemplar "@BKanizay 25 Nov. in *twitter.com* (O.E.D. Archive) Awesomesauce!!! The Muppets sing Bohemian Rhapsody. The most awesome thing you'll see today."
12. *OED*, "stupid," def. B1.
13. *Ibid.*
14. Christine Hoffman, *Stupid Humanism: Folly as Competence in Early Modern and Twenty-First-Century Culture* (New York, 2017), 35. The passage has been the subject of much commentary; for the ambiguities surrounding the ways in which, "for a brief moment his evil separates off," see Neil Forsyth, *The Satanic Epic* (Princeton, 2003), 261-62.
15. Of course this can and has been read as merely a possibility of a perception noted by Milton, as in Stanley Fish's argument that "higher knowledge has *not* fallen degraded in Eve's presence, and, because the possibility has been noted, it is less likely to fall in the future. The delicacy (not frailty) of Adam's understanding is mirrored in the word 'seems,' a verbal extension of his will through which he controls the illusion of Eve's superiority by insisting on its status as illusion." *Surprised by Sin: The Reader in "Paradise Lost"*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge, Mass., 1997), 228.
16. John Reichert, "Against His Better Knowledge': A Case for Adam," *ELH* 48, no. 1 (1981): 87.
17. For Adam's extreme precocity, see John Leonard, *Naming in Paradise: Milton and the Language of Adam and Eve* (Oxford, 1990), 23.
18. C. S. Lewis, *A Preface to "Paradise Lost"* (New York, 1961), 97.
19. *Ibid.*, 99.
20. *A Maske*, lines 811-13.
21. Charles I, *Eikon Basilike* (London, 1649), 165.
22. Richard Perrinchief, "The Life of Charles I," in *Basilike: The Works of King Charles the Martyr* (London, 1687), 55.
23. Jan Kott, *Shakespeare Our Contemporary*, trans. Boleslaw Taborski (New York, 1964).
24. Alex Nichols, "We Live in Hell, So Of Course Jim Bakker Is Here," *The Outline*, March 14, 2019.
25. Allyson Chu, "Brett Kavanaugh Likes Beer, but Not Questions about His Drinking Habits," *Washington Post*, September 28, 2018.
26. Ceylan Yeginsu, "'They're All Idiots': Amid Brexit Chaos, Britains Lose Faith in Politicians," *New York Times*, September 9, 2019.

27. For evidence of America's exceptional embrace of stupidity, see Charles P. Pierce, *Idiot America: How Stupidity Became a Virtue in the Land of the Free* (New York, 2010).
28. Milton, *De Doctrina Christiana*, ed. John K. Hale and J. Donald Cullington, in *Complete Works of John Milton*, vol. 8 (Oxford, 2012), "ardor" or "idignatio," 1026-27.
29. Steven Jablonski, "Hamm's Vicious Race: Slavery and John Milton," *Studies in English Literature, 1500-1900* 37, no. 1 (1997): 186.
30. *Ibid.*
31. See William Riley Parker, *Milton: A Biography*, 2 vols. (Oxford, 1968), 479.